

Thoughts on the legend of Hiram

Ferenc Sebök, 08/11/2017.

Masonic work presented to the Worshipful lodge « Les Vrais Amis, 51 », East of Retinne, working in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, Regular Grand Lodge of Belgium.

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1. Introduction

In the third degree of the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, the ritual speaks of the legend of the murder of Hiram, like a play, with three Brothers who will bring the legend to life. The Worshipful Master called Right Worshipful Master and the two Wardens will be the main actors. In turn, they will play the felonious Fellow crafts demanding the secret word from the Master architect Hiram, who will refuse three times to reveal the word of the Mastery to them.

Hiram will then be struck by each of the felons, by the ruler, the square and finally the mallet, which will deliver the coup de grace. Master Hiram dies and the three felons disappear after their crime. The legend continues with the Fellow craft who is a Master in the making. The latter takes Hiram's place, lying on the ground or in a catafalque, covered with a black shroud.

A branch of Acacia, which is the symbol of imputrescibility and incorruptibility will be found on the shroud, with a Golden Triangle. This branch of Acacia is also the symbol of the Master and is linked to the secret of the Master: "Acacia is known to me!", implying that those who are not masters, "do not know Acacia".

Then, three groups of three Brothers of the Lodge, will turn, successively, around the catafalque, in search of the remains of Hiram the architect. All the Brothers of the Lodge, participate by lowering their heads and partially hiding their faces as a sign of pain and mourning.

The Lodge is plunged into darkness and the aprons are turned back, revealing a black side; on some aprons we see a death's head with seven tears of blood, surrounding the skull. The drama of Hiram's death is at its climax.

And the ritual continues...

2. Reflections on the legend of Hiram of the REAA rite

In the ritual of Master degree in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, the "Master in the making", who is the Fellow craft, to whom the salary increase has been granted, replaces the body of Hiram and in fact symbolizes the door to a "rebirth". This rebirth is preceded by death and has an initiatory value, but also an esoteric and teaching value.

Let us recall that according to Lassalle, J-P. (2004), "the Ancient and Accepted Scottish Rite (AASR), conservatory of Noachism is, in general, the conservatory of the ancient Masonic tradition wanting to stand out from the Masonic tradition stemming from the Grand Lodge of London in 1717.

The predicate "ancient" which qualifies the rite, testifies to this will, and refers to the singular adventure of the Irish around Laurence Dermott who wanted to create a rival Grand Lodge to return to the ancient customs to which the Irish were attached...".

According to Simon, J-P. (2013), "The movement and the trend are obviously prior to the date of 1751 when this other masonry from which the AASR derives visibly appears".

In the AASR rite, the Fellow craft symbolically dies to be born again, discovering new horizons full of pitfalls. But the ritual of the AASR rite calls the Freemason to prudence, which is a cardinal value. In the third degree of the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, for example, we frequently hear:

"I would like to trust my Brothers".

This is a prudence linked to the nature of man with his weaknesses and the continuous work on himself that he must do, to progress and not fall into easy comfort, such as not questioning himself or not advancing his quest for Light. The teaching of the legend is strong: to advance, the Freemason must constantly be a seeker. This quest is intimately linked to spirituality and knowledge of traditions and ritual.

Hiram dies, as the profane dies, during his initiation and is then reborn by receiving the Light after his travels evoking the four elements. This rebirth offers the possibility of progressing towards the Light.

During the ceremony, the three felon Fellow crafts represent the three main officers of the Lodge, that is to say the "three Lights". Attention must therefore be paid to the fact that this legend lies in wait for us every time in our action, if the latter is devoid of wisdom, love and compassion. We risk being dominated by our passions, our beliefs, our certainties. No mason is therefore safe from himself!

The mason must square his stone, with the chisel and the mallet, from the first degree of apprentice, then look in the mirror to see his own judge, during the second degree of Fellow crafts. Hiram dies and is then reborn from his ashes, like the Phoenix, by the Five Points of Perfection of Mastery. "MacBenac" in the modern rite; "Moabon" in the ancient and accepted Scottish rite... "The flesh leaves the bones!" The Brothers agree that the word shouted spontaneously will be the new word of Master.

The instruction in the third degree is symbolically strong. Indeed, the Second Warden, bearer of the Plumb Line should possess sufficient knowledge to curb his passions, without which it is ignorance that would precipitate him into the abysses of felony. The First Warden, for his part, who is bearer of the Level should be able to enlighten the Works of his Brothers, unless his passions, his felony, his fanaticism plunge him into blindness.

The Right Worshipful Master who plays the role of the third felonious Fellow Crafts should direct the Works with wisdom, tolerance and a certain self-denial, far from personal concerns, intrigues aimed at power or keeping power.

My Worshipful Brothers, the legend of Hiram invites us to reflect on our hidden, excessive ambitions... which exceed our quality as masons and throw us into the abysses of megalomania. The mallet is the symbol of authority, certainly, but fraternal, otherwise the mallet becomes a murderous instrument killing Hiram.

The Fellow Craft who has become Master of this Worshipful Lodge, after his initiation (the experience of the legend of Hiram) must have sufficient reflective distance with regard to love for his Brothers in order not to sink into the madness of men. The Lodge becomes a Sacred space, where space-time no longer exists, making way for the seven liberal Arts and the search for spirituality in the sphere of love for one's neighbour.

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The legend of Hiram is a staging of the murder and resurrection of Hiram, which makes this rite become, in a way, the essence of speculative Freemasonry. The legend of Hiram allows us to experience the last phase of the initiation of the mason in the so-called "Blue" Lodge.

The raising of the body by the five points of Perfection allows a symbolic substitution with Hiram, to be reborn again with the warning reflections that I spoke about previously. The new Master thus passes from the horizontal terrestrial plane to the sky, by the vertical plane serving as a hyphen, a link.

This legend makes us discover immanence: "what is Above is Below and what is Below is Above". The accepted death of Hiram finally makes us discover six essential spheres in our life as a mason.

The death of Hiram is linked to the lost word, symbol of the initiate having achieved mastery. According to Bayard J-P. (1982):

"The man in love with spirituality, referring to the traditional value, thinks that everything comes from the Word, the center of knowledge... everything has been said, expressed, but the Word has been lost, at least sufficiently transformed, to no longer be understood".

This statement makes us think first of the story of the Tower of Babel (Old Testament) where men wanting to become God were no longer able to understand each other; then the Volume of the Sacred Law (Bible) opened to the Prologue of John, on which the Compass rests on the Square at the third degree. Indeed, the Prologue also speaks of the Word, but also of the Light in the Darkness.

3. The six spheres of the legend of Hiram

In the legend of Hiram we can discover six spheres that interact at the level of the Fellow Craft's consciousness and at the emotional level, that is to say at the level of his feelings.

The first sphere is of a moral nature.

This sphere is close to probity and the questioning of our actions; it forbids us passions and teaches us what is right. It is also the sphere that allows us to keep the secret of the newly agreed Master. This dimension is also linked to the Oath. This sphere refers us to the requirements to be able to enter Freemasonry: "to be free - honest - of good morals".

The second sphere is of an ethical nature.

It is that of preserving the other, one's Brothers from any aggressiveness linked to passions. This implies restraint, reflection in action. It is also a way of behaving and living with one's Brothers by seeking harmony instead of creating discord, chaos. This requires congruent, empathetic behavior, involving the wisdom sought.

The third sphere has a symbolic value.

In Freemasonry, don't we say that "together we can do everything, alone we can do nothing". The symbolist sphere also concerns the esoteric domain, with a "death-rebirth" alchemy.

The symbolist sphere implies spirituality, the elevation of the spirit, the search for truth, the understanding of the Sacred. For this, the Freemason has tools at his disposal that he must use spiritually to try to pierce its mysteries. The practiced ritual is allowing him to better understand the importance of symbolic tools.

The fourth sphere is of an initiatory nature for the Freemason.

The legend of Hiram experienced by the Fellow Craft is an initiation. The Fellow Craft is a Master in the making, but he is suspected of the murder and his apron is brought to the Worshipful Master, called Right Worshipful Master in the third degree of the Ancient and accepted Scottish Rite.

During the legend lived by the Fellow Craft, he is tested, killed, then finally raised by the "Five Points of Perfection", which is the symbolism of death and resurrection.

The new Master must perceive that he is becoming a new being, who must engage in the path of spiritual research. His quest must not find rest, since he must overcome his passions and constantly make progress in Freemasonry. This progress must be achieved on himself. The fight thus concerns three dimensions:

- overcome his passions
- make progress in Freemasonry
- cultivate shared brotherly love.

It is interesting to note that for Viot, M. (1981):

"Initiation is accessible to all free men, capable of overcoming their dogma or their absence of dogma. The agnostic and the religious therefore have their place among us".

The fifth sphere has a teaching value.

This teaching implies what the Freemason already knows, but this initiation will invite him to rediscover "V.I.T.R.I.O.L" by the necessary step back from what he experiences during this initiation and by the way of introspection.

The legend of Hiram makes us discover man and his universe in relation to death and the divine breath (Ruah in Hebrew or Pneuma, in Latin).

Ruah is inspiration expiration, but also death gestation, like a cellular death followed by cellular renewal. This manifestation also recalls the appearance disappearance of the stars. Microcosm and macrocosm are in symbiosis and the four elements earth - air - water - fire - interact. Thus, what is above is below and vice versa.

This also reminds us, like humans, of the rite of the sun which is eternal.

This also reminds us of the Winter Solstice followed by the Summer Solstice where we see the Sun reborn, reappearing. Master Hiram comes out of his tomb

to return to the life, with the convenience of a new word replacing the lost word. In the ancient and accepted Scottish Rite, this word will be "Macbenac... the flesh leaves the bones."

The sixth sphere concerns the heart of the Freemason.

If there is reason, there is also the heart. The heart is linked to brotherly love, tolerance, compassion and the charitable spirit, which is a theological value. This sixth sphere reminds us of the "Tipheret" in the Sephirot. It also reminds us of the emotions necessary in human relationships.

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My Worshipful Brothers, I will end this instruction board as follows:

The legend of Hiram reminds us of our duty to build the Universal chain, and not to destroy it, at the risk of becoming a bad Fellow Craft. This legend refers us to Creation rather than to Death, which is only a passage. Does the spiritual man have nothing to do with the divine?

Each human is different from others, with his perceptions, his mental images of the other, his beliefs and his certainties and the notion of good seem very relative. This is the reason why we must respect the freedom of others.

Swedenborg, E. (1758) says the following (87):

"As the good in each is different, it follows that it is the quality of the good that determines to what degree and in what proportion each is the neighbour".

The Freemason will have to work on himself to go beyond this statement and to have an open mind, and a fraternal spirit. However, the things of life have programmed us and we tend to have a conditional love.

Traditional Freemasonry is marked by spiritual research, respecting the "Landmarks" whose founding text is called the "Anderson Constitutions" of 1723. Man must be worthy to become a Freemason.

This dignity must be part of fraternal love. In addition to this, is it not required at the entrance of the Temple, that the mason must be free, probe and of good morals?

These qualities are safeguards at the entrance of a Profane.

Freedom implies the fact that the mason can get rid of his passions, his inclinations and that he can be capable of questioning himself. Freedom implies that the Mason can distance himself from beliefs and certainties.

The Freemason freely chooses to walk towards the Light, but this also implies a curious, critical and tolerant spirit.

As Malfait, G. (1987) says in « Travaux de la Loge nationale de recherches Villard de Honnecourt », n°15, GLNF, 1987:

“Man, his Brother, the Freemason will never tire of seeking it, in its profound richness, in the diversity of his opinions, his beliefs, his traditions, without rejecting any of them, a priori, without being afraid to advance into unknown territory, without exclusivity, without anathema, without the will to power, without totalitarianism of thought.”

Probity has a close relationship with fidelity and always seeking what is right. Probity inspires trust and implies that the mason respects his oaths, his commitments. As such, the mason must not be perjured.

Good morals concern the moral sense of the Freemason. As such, he must become an example, a beacon transmitting the light he receives. The theological values Faith – Hope – Charity complete the way of “being and doing” of the Freemason. My Brothers, “The Light shines in the Darkness, but the Darkness has not comprehended it”. Let us walk towards the Light rather than sinking into Darkness and Chaos.

Encre sur papier carton, 30x40, Ferenc Sebök, 2022.

Encre sur carton, 20x15, Ferenc Sebök, 2011.

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What is Above is Below, ink on cardboard 30x40, Ferenc Sebök, 2024.